

СПОСІБ МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ ОЖИРІННЯ У СТАТЕВОЗРІЛИХ ЩУРІВ ЛІНІЇ WISTAR

METHOD FOR MODELING OBESITY IN MATURE RATES OF THE WISTAR LINE

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Анотація: Морфологічні дослідження чоловічої статеві системи дуже актуальні у сучасному житті. Особливо це стосується чоловічого безпліддя, доброякісної гіперплазії та раку передміхурової залози. При цьому епідеміологічні дослідження показують, що частота розвитку цих захворювань зростає у людей з надлишковою масою тіла, у хворих з метаболічним синдромом, котрий характеризується поєднанням таких факторів, як абдомінальне ожиріння, артеріальна гіпертонія, атеросклероз, порушення ліпідного обміну, інсулінорезистентність, андрогенний дефіцит.

Annotation: Morphological studies of the male reproductive system are very relevant in modern life. This is especially true of male infertility, benign hyperplasia, and prostate cancer. Epidemiological studies show that the incidence of these diseases increases in overweight people, and in patients with metabolic syndrome, which is characterized by a combination of factors such as obesity, hypertension, atherosclerosis, disorders of lipid metabolism, and insulin resistance.

Introduction

Increased interest in the problem of obesity and metabolic syndrome is due to the fact that the frequency of these disorders in most countries is growing at an epidemic rate. The main reason for this phenomenon is considered to be the widespread way of life, which is called "Western". This stereotype of behavior includes insufficient physical activity, combined with high calories and fats of animal origin and poor vegetables and fruits in the diet. Obesity is the result of a long-term violation of the energy balance when energy intake in the body exceeds its energy expenditure [1]. An important component of the mechanisms of pathogenesis of obesity is the actual adipose tissue, which has endo, auto- and paracrine functions [2].

Material and methods of research: 20 prostate glands of Wistar rats at the age of 120 days were studied. In the experiment, the animals were divided into 2 groups: 1 - intact; 2- experimental with the simulation of experimental obesity. Intact for 2

months received a standard diet and water ad libitum. Rats of the 2nd group, for 2 months were on a high-calorie diet of C 11024 and water ad libitum (West D. _ B. _ et . al ., 1992). Feed consumption was monitored daily, and rats were weighed once a week. After 2 months of the experiment, rats were selected from a group of experimental animals to obtain biological material. Pieces of the prostate were fixed in 10% buffered neutral formalin, sections were made according to conventional methods, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin. All data were processed statistically (software package Statistica 6.0).

The results of the study and their discussion: We found that rats with experimental obesity have significant morphological changes in the prostate: there is an intense decrease in glandular epithelium by 50%, glandular epithelial cells decrease in size (flatten), and glandular lumen narrows, leading to decreased secretory activity and stagnation of secretion excretory ducts of the gland. There is a significant growth of connective tissue with aggregation of adipocytes. Changes in the microcirculatory system were revealed.

Conclusions: It has been experimentally proven that morphological changes in the pancreas with experimental obesity indicate a lack of pancreatic function in such animals, which leads to a decrease in secretion and impaired excretion. Our attention was drawn to the study of the effects of glutamate on the reproductive system, namely the prostate gland. The urgency of this problem is related to the prevalence of diseases and complications that occur with poor nutrition.

References:

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